

Sensitive Hemoglobin Concentration Sensor Based on Graphene-Plasmonic Nano-structures with Review of Applications

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ABSTRACT: Hemoglobin concentration sensors are created in this study using a row of half-cylindrical rods. The suggested structures are capable of accurately detecting blood sample hemoglobin concentrations. Two different topologies based on graphene-plasmonic couples are proposed and explored and a comprehensive review is included in this work. The proposed structures are composed of various layers of graphene, SiO₂, Au, and Ag. Multiple plates and cylindrical-shaped graphene layers are added to the structures to improve the functionality (absorption peak value and wavelength) of the absorber (sensor). By adding more Au layers, the confinement of the incident electromagnetic waves is tightened and the absorption factor is raised. The theoretical background is summarized and the intrinsic nature of graphene plasmons, interactions between graphene and SPPs induced by metallic nanostructures and the electrical control of SPPs by adjusting the Fermi level of graphene are discussed. Subsequently, the development of optical sensors, biological sensors and important components such as absorbers/emitters and reconfigurable optical mirrors for use in new sensor systems are reviewed. To improve the results, the suggested configurations also include how the chemical potential of the graphene layers and "G" (graphene layer thicknesses) affect the absorption peak and wavelength. The final recommended structure shows a unity absorption peak and is therefore applicable to a variety of situations. The structure is taken into consideration as a refractive index bio-sensor for measuring hemoglobin concentrations in blood samples, indicating a respectable sensitivity factor of 570 nm/RIU.

Keywords: Bio-sensor · Graphene · Hemoglobin Concentration · Plasmonic · Refractive index sensor

Introduction

Optical bio-sensors have received a lot of attention recently. Compared to conventional ones, optical bio-sensors show far more outstanding functionalities. They gain the benefits of increased sensitivity, decreased cost, smaller sizes, and increased sensitivity precisions [1]. These sensors can be used specifically in medical systems, biotechnology labs, and other scholarly areas [2]. Graphene-plasmonic pairings may lead to optical biosensors. Surface plasmon resonances (SPR) are a basis for the operation of plasmonic-graphene nanostructures [4-6]. Interesting characteristics of graphene plasmonic composites include high optical conflation [3],

extremely low losses, and their excellent electromagnetic (EM) tunability candidates for THz spectral range sensors [7]. Plasmonic Metal and semiconductor combinations are used to create nanostructures. Although graphene has layers of carbon atoms, dielectrics are set up in lattices of two dimensions [8]. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which is created when the EM light wave interacts with free metal electrons, frees the light from the limitations placed on it by the diffraction of light in nano-scaled dimensions (lower than the propagating wavelengths). Because of this, graphene-plasmonic structures can be successfully applied as absorbers [9-10], temperature and refractive index sensors [11], or bio-sensors for the detection of significant

substances like hemoglobin and glucose [12]. Different methods can be used to create graphene-plasmonic-based nanostructures [13, 14]. Numerous methods can be used to design plasmonic graphene-based sensors. For creating precise and sensitive biosensors, Refractive Index (RI)-based structures make suitable candidates [15, 16]. Interesting studies taking into account various plasmonic-graphene nanostructure configurations have been described. For instance, the finite element technique (FEM) was used to examine the optical characteristics of plasmonic materials in the form of gold nano-rods [17]. The plasmon-mode wave functions caused the spatially oscillating patterns to be visible on the surface. Another study [18] used the FEM method to conduct numerical analyses of adjustable SPRs and dipole cavity plasmon modes of the scattering cross-section (SCS) on various nano-rod designs. The solid-gold/gold-shell nano-rods can be tweaked and regulated to produce particular wavelengths due to the various features of these structures [18]. Another study proposed and looked into a sensor based on plasmonic-dielectric pairings with various dielectric core plasmonic metamaterials [19]. The proposed structure has demonstrated highly intriguing and useful findings by combining lattice resonance, localized SPR, and cavity plasmon resonance modes [19].

An SPR biosensor with a RI range of 1 to 1.0007 was demonstrated in a different study for the detection of blood glucose levels between 25 and 175 mg/dl. The suggested sensor's 275.15 /RIU degree of sensitivity was appropriate. In recent studies, graphene-based biosensors were recommended for virus detection due to their superior affordability, accuracy, and speed in light of the COVID-19 pandemic [20]. In another study, the idea of a graphene-plasmonic biosensor was considered. Layers of a graphene sheet and silver nanoparticles formed the foundation of the construction. The structure had a graphene thickness of 9 nm, which resulted in a 304.6% increase in sensitivity over the non-graphene structure [21]. Also, plasmonic nanostructures with different shapes (sphere, cubic, cylindrical) were proposed for hemoglobin concentration sensing [22]. The results indicated different resonance wavelengths for the three nano-particle shapes. It is declared that, by managing and engineering tunable properties of graphene-based nanostructures, they can be effectively used as biosensors for different applications [23]. Another study suggests a graphene-gold combination structure for identifying biomolecules and biological cells, such as blood, glucose, and other substances, by taking into account their refractive indices [24].

Table 1. Geometric parameters of Fig. 2

Parameters	Value(nm)
R	650
t	20
d	1400
g	0.340
P	750

In all of the mentioned reports, the applications of graphene-plasmonic nano-structures in sensors and especially biosensors were stated and considered. In this work, novel sensitive biosensors based on graphene-plasmonic combinations are proposed. As shown in Figure 1a–c, graphene comprises atomically-thin carbon sheets having a hexagonal lattice structure. This material exhibits unique optical and electrical properties because of its Dirac cone-type bandgap structure, where the energy depends linearly on the wave vector around the K point [14–16]. Specifically, graphene has exceptional electrical, optical and chemical properties that are well-suited to sensor applications and that are not achievable with conventional technologies based on bulk materials [17]. These characteristics include high carrier mobility, fast photo-response, broadband photodetection from the ultraviolet to the THz regions of the spectrum, flexibility and low cost [18]. Thus, graphene and other two-dimensional materials are the focus of an increasing number of research studies and novel phenomena associated with these materials are still being discovered [19]. At the same time, new applications such as high-speed transistors [20], photodetectors [21,22], biological sensors [23,24], gas sensors [25], energy storage [26], displays [27] and flexible devices [28] are being proposed based on the novel physics of such materials [29,30].

Fig. 1. (a) A schematic illustration of the atomic arrangement in graphene. (b) The honeycomb lattice (left) and the Brillouin zone (right) for graphene. a_1 and a_2 are the lattice unit vectors. b_1 and b_2 are the reciprocal lattice vectors. (c) The energy bands in the vicinity of the K and K' points.

In particular, graphene can serve as a plasmonic material operating in the mid-IR to THz regions of the spectrum and its optical constants (such as permittivity and refractive index) can be adjusted by applying a gate voltage [31], which cannot be achieved by conventional metal-based plasmonic materials. Therefore, graphene-based plasmonic-type sensors show promise with regard to meeting the recent demand for devices operating in the mid-IR to THz regions with electrically tunable wavelengths.

Biological sensor

Graphene has also shown promise as a component of biological sensors, as it has a large surface area and is biocompatible with antibodies, enzymes, DNA, cells and proteins [24]. In particular, surface-enhanced infrared absorption (SEIRA) can significantly enhance the sensitivity in the IR wavelength range using SPPs [89]. Therefore, graphene plasmonic has become an important component of the recent development of biological sensors. Figure 6 [71] presents a schematic of a proposed GNR-based biosensor that takes advantage of graphene SPPs [47,51]. Incident IR irradiation generates SPR across the GNRs. The electromagnetic field is strongly localized at the GNR edges, which enhances the interaction between the IR rays and the protein molecules adsorbed on the GNRs. Such sensors are based on other principles and as outlined in the introduction [58]. In these devices, the electromagnetic field generated by the graphene SPPs is concentrated at the GNR edges and increases the light-matter interactions of molecules adsorbed on the graphene. Proteins can be recognized by monitoring the SPR spectral shifts associated with narrow dips corresponding to the molecular vibration bands of the protein. Moreover, the gate voltage tunability of graphene-based SPR enables continuous sweeping over the protein vibrational bands [90].

Fig. 2. (a) A schematic showing the concept of a GNR-based biosensor and (b) an SEM image of a GNR array. Both figures are adapted from Reference [80]. © 2020 The American Association for the Advancement of Science.

Absorbers and Emitters

Graphene-based absorbers are very similar to graphene-based photoelectric sensors in terms of the enhancement of the absorbers. Graphene-based emitters are also important light sources in various analytical applications, such as gas analysis systems. Both graphene-based emitters and absorbers operate on the same principle based on Planck's law [58] and the present section focuses on absorbers. The majority of graphene-based absorbers incorporate plasmonic metamaterials or meta-surface absorbers (PMAs) that operate according to principles as explained in [87]. These devices can be classified into two groups according to their function (1) those that increase absorption by enhancing the quantum efficiency of graphene and (2) reconfigurable optical devices involving the modulation of the absorption wavelength.

Absorption Enhancement

PMAs have attracted significant interest because they exhibit near-unity absorbance along with wavelength selectivity while allowing small device dimensions [85,89]. Although graphene-based PMAs without metal-based plasmonic structures have been investigated, various types of PMAs with graphene have also been researched. These have included one-dimensional gratings [50], 2D plasmonic crystals [66,69], bow-tie antennae and MIM structures [78–80]. These devices are being examined because graphene-based PMAs without metal-based plasmonic structures have narrow operation wavelength bands [53,61,63] and low absorbance values [81]. The majority of such units use MIM-based PMAs and Figure 5 presents a typical example of a MIM-based PMA incorporating graphene. Figure 3a, b,d provide schematic illustrations of the graphene layers formed on the top of the device [31],

on the top and in the middle of the insulator layers and on the top of the micro-patches [88].

Figure 3. Graphene integrated metamaterial absorbers. (a) A schematic of graphene embedded in an MIM absorber using hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) and (b) schematics of graphene coated over top of MIM absorbers together with absorbance data for graphene in the middle and the top of the insulator layers. (c) The absorbance plots of this device for various chemical potentials. (d) The absorbance of graphene coated over top of metal-insulator-metal (MIM) absorbers. (a) is reprinted from Reference [75] with the permission of AIP Publishing. (b–d) were adapted with permission from Reference [90]. © 2020 Optical Society of America.

Interestingly, the absorbance of such devices will change according to the location of the graphene layers, indicating that the localized SPPs (LSPs) induced by the MIM-based PMA can enhance the absorption of the graphene. It is important to note that the positioning of the graphene and the thickness of the insulator layer are also important factors, in addition to the chemical potential of the graphene resulting from matching of the surface optical impedance [60]. These devices can function both as high-performance electromagnetic absorbers and as advanced thermal IR or THz sensors. Figure 3c plots the absorbance data for various graphene chemical potentials and demonstrates the possibility of electrically tuning the absorbance, as discussed in the next section.

Absorption Wavelength Modulation

As discussed in Section 2.2, the optical conductivity of graphene can be tuned by applying a voltage, such that the modulation of SPP wavelengths can be achieved using metallic nanostructures. Typically, this modulation is associated with the integration of graphene with meta-surfaces [70], split rings [62,68,79] or other metamaterials [38–44] or with metallic nanoparticles [55,56]. Figure 5 shows a typical example of the modulation of the device reflection and the reflection phase by adjusting the extent of doping of the graphene. The device structure consists of a MIM-based PMA with embedded graphene, which is similar to those in Figure 3.

Figure 4. (a) A schematic of a reflect-array of rod antennas integrated with graphene. (b) The calculated reflection spectra (upper panel) and phase of the reflected light (lower panel) for various graphene doping levels. Both figures are reprinted from Reference [83] with the permission of AIP Publishing.

Figure 4b, demonstrates that both the reflection and the phase can be significantly adjusted by modifying the extent of doping. Interestingly, this same effect can be realized using meta-surfaces without gold plates as substrates. Although the surface conductivity of graphene is minimal, the interaction is strengthened when graphene interacts with the strong electric fields of SPPs generated by currents in the metallic nanostructures [72]. This electrical tuning effect can be used in a wide range of applications, such as advanced IR, biological [77] and gas sensors, as well as in other optical devices including band stop filters [38], waveguides [28,65] and cloaking units [71]. In particular, the electrical control of the phase of the reflected light could potentially permit dynamic control of the light direction in future sensing systems.

Figure 5. (a) A schematic illustration of a phase modulator based on graphene embedded with metallic resonators. (b) An SEM image of the resonators. (c) The absorption spectra for various graphene Fermi levels. (d) A schematic illustration of a reconfigurable reflector based on graphene embedded in MIM-based meta-surfaces. (a–c) are adapted from Reference [89]. © 2020 American Chemical Society. (d) is adapted from reference [90]. © 2020 American Chemical Society.

This same concept can be employed in other wavelength regions, such as the visible and near-IR. However, there are still challenges associated with this technology, including achieving high efficiencies, the suppression of higher order diffractions, variations in the uniformity of the graphene and the appropriate fabrication of the metallic nanostructures. Control of the transmission of light [55] or light focusing [60], such as normally provided by a lens, could also be realized based on this concept. The resulting beam steering devices in conjunction with optical sensors could be used in advanced driver assistance systems and drone technology.

Geometry, Theoretical Model, and Numerical Method

The first proposed structure is a combination of graphene, Au, Ag, and SiO₂ layers as depicted in Fig. 1. The structure consists of the periodic pattern of half cylindrical-shaped arrays of Au rods placed above Ag, graphene, and SiO₂ layers. The geometric parameters of Fig. 2 are tabulated in Table 1.

In the structure as shown in Fig. 1a, a plane wave polarized in the z-axis with 1-W power is applied as the incident field. The periodic boundary condition is considered in the x-direction. Considering the finite element (FEM) method, the field distributions at resonance wavelength of 1053 nm, in Fig. 3a; non-resonance wavelength of 1040 nm, in Fig. 3b; and the absorption and reflection spectrum, in Fig. 3c, are simulated and shown. A simple equation can show the relationship between the transmission, absorption, and reflection fields [16, 27]:

$$A(\omega) = 1 - R(\omega) - T(\omega) \quad (1)$$

Considering $T(\omega) = 0$, then from (1), it is clear that $A(\omega) = 1 - R(\omega)$. As it is considered to achieve the perfect absorption parameter (to have the proper sensor), the reflection parameter $R(\omega)$ should equal zero which leads to a unity value for absorption ($A(\omega)$). As a result, the incident light wave would be thoroughly absorbed leading to the increment of the absorption peak value. The surface conductivity of a graphene layer can be considered by the Kubo formula [16, 28,36]:

$$\sigma_g(\omega, \mu_c, \Gamma, T) = \sigma_{g-real} + j\sigma_{g-imag} = \sigma_{int real} + \sigma_{int er} \quad (2)$$

where ω , μ_c , Γ , and T indicate the operation frequency, the chemical potential, the phenomenological scattering rate, and the absolute temperature, respectively. The intra-band and inter-band electro-photon scattering parameters can also be described as [16, 28]:

$$\sigma_{int er} = -j \frac{e^2 k_B T}{\pi \hbar^2 (\omega - j2\Gamma)} \times \left[\frac{\mu_c}{k_B T} + 2 \ln \left(\exp \left(-\frac{\mu_c}{k_B T} \right) + 1 \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{int er} = -j \frac{e^2}{4\pi \hbar} \ln \left[\frac{2|\mu_c| - (\omega - j2\Gamma)\hbar}{2|\mu_c| + (\omega - j2\Gamma)\hbar} \right] \quad (4)$$

where k_B , T , and e are Boltzmann constant, temperature, and electron charge, respectively. Drude model can introduce the dielectric function of the metals as [29–31]:

$$\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 - j\omega\gamma} \quad (5)$$

where $\epsilon_\infty = 3.7$ (dielectric constant at infinite frequency), $\gamma = 0.018$ eV (collision plasma angular frequency), and $\omega_p = 9.1$ eV (bulk plasma angular frequency) [29–31]. As can be seen from Fig. 6 (c), the absorption peak of 0.8 at 1053 nm is obtained. To improve the absorption peak and functionality of the structure, other combinations of graphene and plasmonic layers would be presented.

Fig. 6 (a) Schematic of the first proposed structure.

(b) View of the single array of the structure

Results and Discussion

In this section, 2 different structures based on the combinations of graphene-plasmonic layers in the shape of half-cylindrical arrays are presented. It is important to notice that considering more layers of graphene and Au can affect the characteristics of the structures and increase their absorption peaks [27, 32]. Therefore, their effects on the absorption spectrum will be discussed. The first structure was considered and evaluated in Fig. 7. The absorption

Fig. 7. a Field distribution at $\lambda=1053$ nm. b Field distribution at $\lambda=1040$ nm. c Schematic of the absorption and reflection spectrum

peak value of 0.8 at wavelength of 1053 nm was achieved. The following proposed structures are proposed in order to improve the functionality of the structure by enhancing the absorption peak

Fig.8 (a) Schematic of the second proposed structure. (b) View of the single array of the structure

Conclusion

This review examined graphene plasmonic with regard to potential sensors applications. This phenomenon has opened up new fields concerning the use of SPPs in the mid-IR and THz regions, as a direct result of the Dirac cone band structure of graphene. As a consequence, high-performance optical sensors operating at IR wavelengths and at ambient temperature can be realized using graphene SPPs induced by GNRs. Graphene-based optical sensors with plasmonic nanostructures also show promise as high-responsivity wavelength- or polarization selective functional devices. Two different configurations based on graphene-plasmonic nano-structures were considered for bio-sensing applications. These structures were made of half-cylindrical shaped rods of graphene and Au which were organized on different layers of Ag, SiO₂, and graphene. In order to improve the functionality of the structures, effects of chemical potential and graphene layer's thicknesses on the absorption peak and wavelength were also studied. By applying more cylindrical-shaped layers of Au and graphene, the absorption peaks experienced higher values. The final suggested structure, which showed unity absorption peak, was considered the refractive index sensor for detecting hemoglobin concentrations in blood samples. By considering RI values of $n=1.335$ for 3.5 g/dl, $n=1.34$ for 10.6 g/dl,

$n=1.36$ for 16.5 g/dl, $n=1.385$ for 28.7 g/dl, the acceptable sensitivity factor of 570 nm/RIU was achieved. As a result, the proposed structures can be interesting and great candidates for the detection of different bio-elements and tissues and can be appropriate bio-sensors. Biological sensors based on graphene SPPs also exhibit higher performance and wavelength-tunable operation. In addition, work to date shows that graphene-based absorbers and reconfigurable absorbers will be important components of future sensing systems with applications in gas analysis, chemical analysis, alcohol detection and LiDAR. Taking advantage of graphene enables these optical components to operate at specific desired wavelengths as a result of electrostatic gating. Recent advances in other 2D materials as well as in the fabrication of heterostructures and in all-dielectric meta-surfaces are expected to address the intrinsic loss effects associated with graphene SPPs and enable the development of next generation sensors having a wide range of uses, such as for the analysis of images, biological compounds, gases and chemicals. It is hoped that this review will contribute to the development of advanced sensors using graphene plasmonic and the expansion of the range of associated applications.

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